

**The Multi-visit Drone Routing Problem with Edge Launches:
An Iterative Approach with Discrete and Continuous Improvements**

Online Supplement

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Online supplement A

This online supplement contains the MVDRP formulation and the details about the RTS algorithm proposed in [24].

MVDRP formulation

An integer programming formulation for the MVDRP is proposed in [24]. It is based on the concept of operation. An operation is a set of actions beginning and terminating with the tandem located at a launch location $i \in V$ and at a rendezvous location $j \in V$, respectively. The drone may launch from the truck in i , visit one or more customers, then rendezvous with the truck at j . As previously indicated, a MVDRP operation requires that after a drone launch from i , the truck must travel directly from i to j without stopping. A drone flight (sortie) is allowed within an operation only when it is weight and energy feasible. A drone sortie is considered weight and energy feasible if the combined weight of all packages delivered in the sortie is less than w_{max} and if it consumes less than e_{max} energy.

Formally, given a drone sortie starting from $i \in V$, serving (in order) customers $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n$, and returning to the truck at $j \in V$, then the sortie is weight feasible if and only if:

$$w_{sum} = \sum_{i \in \{1,2,\dots,n\}} w_i \leq w_{max},$$

and it is energy feasible if and only if:

$$e(i, c_1, w_{sum}) * t_d(i, c_1) + \sum_{k=2}^n e(c_{k-1}, c_k, w_{sum} - \sum_{a=1}^k w_a) * t_d(c_{k-1}, c_k) + e(c_n, j, 0) * t_d(c_n, j) + HOV * \max\{0, t_t(i, j) - DroneTime\} \leq e_{max},$$

where $e(a, b, w)$ is the energy spent by a drone carrying one or more parcels of total weight w from a to b and $DroneTime = t_d(i, c_1) + \sum_{k=1}^n t_d(c_{k-1}, c_k) + t_d(c_n, j)$. An operation is infeasible if the constituent drone flight is weight or energy infeasible. On this basis, let O be the set of all feasible MVDRP operations. For each operation $o, o \in O$ we indicate with: $TruckTime(o)$, the travel time for the truck from the launch point to the retrieval point of the operation; $DroneTime(o)$ the time required for the drone to fly from the launch point of o , visit all customers that it has been assigned as part of the operation (in order), then return to the retrieval point of the operation. If the drone does not launch in o , then $DroneTime(o) = 0$. Then, we define the parameters: $cover(o, j)$ that has value 1 only if operation o services customer c_j , 0 otherwise; $lp(o, l)$ that is equal to 1 whenever operation o begins at location $l, l \in V$, 0 otherwise; $rp(o, l)$ that is equal to 1 if operation o terminates at location $l, l \in V$, 0 otherwise. On the basis of this notation, with x_o a binary variable equal to 1 if the operation o is selected as part of the solution, 0 otherwise, $\forall o \in O$, it is possible to introduce the integer linear programming formulation proposed in [24] for the MVDRP:

$$\min \sum_{o \in O} t_o x_o \tag{S1}$$

s.t.

$$t_o \geq TruckTime(o), \quad \forall o \in O \tag{S2}$$

$$t_o \geq DroneTime(o), \quad \forall o \in O \tag{S3}$$

$$\text{cover}(o, j)x_o \geq 1, \quad \forall j \in C \quad (S4)$$

$$\sum_{o \in O} rp(o, l)x(o) = \sum_{o \in O} lp(o, l)x(o), \quad \forall l \in V \quad (S5)$$

$$\text{subtour elimination constraints} \quad (S6)$$

$$x_o \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall o \in O \quad (S7)$$

The objective function (S1) minimizes the total route completion time, as the sum of individual operation times. Constraints (S2/S3) ensure that the time required for an operation is at least as large as the time required for the truck/drone to perform the operation. Indeed, the two vehicles must be together at the beginning and at the end of the operation due to the definition of operation. Constraints (S4) guarantee that every customer is serviced (covered). Constraints (S5) are flow constraints, which ensure a closed tour. Constraints (S6) are generic constraints to ensure the truck tour is not disjoint. Constraints (S7) express the nature of the variables.

RTS algorithm : Details

The RTS algorithm consists of three steps. In the first step, called *Route*, the customer visit order is determined by solving a Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) over the customers. Given a set of customers, C , a TSP is solved on C where each customer is connected to each other customer by an edge whose weight is equal to the time needed by a drone to go from one customer to the other one. The output of this step is a sequence of customers $\{c_1, \dots, c_{|C|}\}$ which indicates the fixed order according to which the customers will be served in the final solution.

In the second step, called *Transform*, a graph G' is constructed to represent all the possible routes for the tandem given the customer visit order determined in the first step. This step is the fundamental one of the algorithm. It is based on the concept of an *operation*. An operation for the RTS is a movement of the tandem such that at the beginning and at the end of the operation the drone and truck are together in the same locations. Its expression consists of a 4-tuple (i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) which means that the operation begins with the tandem located at the vertex i_1 in a state where the first j_1 customers have been serviced and ends with the tandem at the vertex i_2 in a state where the first j_2 customers have been serviced. This expression also provides information about truck and drone routes within the operation. Indeed, we can retrieve this information on the basis of i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2 as follows:

- If $i_1 \neq i_2 \wedge j_1 = j_2$, then the truck carried the drone from i_1 to i_2 . Because $j_1 = j_2$, no customers were serviced.
- If $i_1 = i_2 \wedge j_1 < j_2$, then the truck stops at i_1 and the customers in $[c_{j_1+1}, \dots, c_{j_2}]$ are served. If the position of the served customers is equal to the position of i_1 , then the truck serves these customers. Otherwise, the drone makes the deliveries moving from customer to customer while the truck waits at i_1 .
- If $i_1 \neq i_2 \wedge j_1 < j_2$, then the truck launches the drone at i_1 and moves to the rendezvous location at i_2 . The drone serves all the customers in $[c_{j_1+1}, \dots, c_{j_2}]$.

It is also possible to compute the maximum weight carried by a drone during an operation, which is its weight at take-off. Let w_c be the weight of the package demanded by customer c . The maximum weight carried by a drone within the operation (i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) is given by the following expression:

$$w(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) = \sum_{k=j_1+1}^{j_2} w_k .$$

Moreover, the weight carried by the drone after servicing customer c_a but before arriving to customer c_{a+1} , such that $j_1 + 1 \leq a \leq j_2$, may be computed as $w(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) - \sum_{k=j_1+1}^a w_k$. That is, the take-off weight minus the sum of the weights of packages already delivered within the operation.

The time needed to perform the operation (i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) may be expressed as:

$$t(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) = \max\{t_d(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2), t_t(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2)\} + I * LaunchP$$

where:

$$t_t(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) = d_t(i_1, i_2) / Speed_t,$$

$$t_d(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) = (d_d(i_1, c_{j_1+1}) + \sum_{x=j_1+1}^{j_2-1} d_d(c_x, c_{x+1}) + d_d(c_{j_2}, i_2)) / Speed_d,$$

t_t represents the amount of time required for the truck to travel from i_1 to i_2 . t_d represents the amount of time for the drone to go from launch location i_1 , service customers $[c_{j_1+1}, \dots, c_{j_2}]$ (in order), then return to the truck at i_2 . If $t_d > 0$ then indicator variable I takes value 1, which effectively imposes the overhead launch penalty; if $t_d = 0$, then $I = 0$ and no launch penalty is assessed. The functions $d_t(i_1, i_2)$ and $d_d(i_1, i_2)$ output the distance which has to be covered by a truck and a drone to go from i_1 to i_2 , respectively. $Speed_t$ ($Speed_d$) is the speed of the truck (drone).

Because we can compute the weight of packages carried and the duration of each flight segment of the drone within an operation, we can also compute the total energy expenditure. Let $e(i_1, i_2, w)$ be the function which expresses the amount of energy spent by a drone moving from i_1 to i_2 carrying a weight equal to w and let hov be a constant that indicates the rate of energy consumption per unit time for a drone, whenever it is hovering. The energy expenditure (ee) of an operation (i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) can be computed as follows:

$$ee(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) = e(i_1, c_{j_1+1}, \sum_{k=j_1+1}^{j_2} w_k) + \sum_{x=j_1+1}^{j_2-1} e(c_x, c_{x+1}, \sum_{k=x+1}^{j_2-1} w_k) +$$

$$e(c_{j_2}, i_2, 0) + hov * \max\{0, t_t(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) - t_d(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2)\}.$$

The first three terms in the energy expenditure expression represent the energy required by the drone to move from the launch position to the first customer, to go from one customer to the next in $[c_{j_1+1}, \dots, c_{j_2}]$, and to move from the last customer to the landing position, respectively. The fourth term expresses the energy spent by the drone if it must wait for the truck at the landing position. Indeed, the drone cannot land if the truck has not yet arrived, so it must hover until the truck has reached the rendezvous position.

Once the concept of operation has been defined, it is possible to explain the *Transform* phase of the algorithm, where graph G' is constructed. This process takes as input the vertices of the original network $G = (V, E)$ representing the road network and generates $|C| + 1$ copies for each vertex in V . In particular, for a vertex i in V we will generate the vertices $\{(i, 0), (i, 1), \dots, (i, |C| - 1), (i, |C|)\}$ in V' . In this way, we are linking each vertex copy to a different number of served customers. Hence, a vertex of G' is denoted by $v'_{i,j} \in V'$ to represent the original vertex $i \in V$ in a state where customers $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j$ have been serviced. Thus, an operation (i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) may be thought of as an arc in G' , linking v'_{i_1, j_1} to v'_{i_2, j_2} . The cost of the arc $(v'_{i_1, j_1}, v'_{i_2, j_2})$ is equal to the time needed to perform the corresponding operation, $t(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2)$, if the operation is feasible. Considering the weight and energy constraints, it is possible to

FIGURE 8 At left, we depict conceptually a solution path through the graph G' . Each row corresponds with some launch/landing location. Each column corresponds to a number of completed deliveries. Arrows connect the start and end location and state of each operation. At right, is the associated representation of the physical path of the solution. The red square is the depot location. Green and yellow squares represent locations of customers and possible launch/landing sites, respectively. Solid black lines show the path of the truck; dashed black lines show the path of the drone.

formally define the arc set (i.e., the set of feasible operations), A' , of the new graph G' as follows:

$$A' = \{ (v'_{i_1 j_1}, v'_{i_2 j_2}) : (j_1 \leq j_2) \wedge ee(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) \leq e_{max} \wedge w(i_1, j_1, i_2, j_2) \leq w_{max} \}.$$

Therefore, at the end of the second phase, a directed graph $G' = (V', A')$ is built, in which the cardinality of V' is equal to $|V| * (|C| + 1)$.

Finally, in the last step of RTS (*Shortest Path*), the heuristic solution to the MVDRP is determined by solving a Shortest Path Problem on the graph G' . Indeed, once the graph G' has been constructed, it is possible to determine a MVDRP solution solving a shortest path problem on G' where the origin is the vertex corresponding to the depot with no customer served ($v'_{depot,0}$) and the destination is the vertex corresponding to the depot with every customer served ($v'_{depot,|C|+1}$).

An example of a MVDRP solution on G' is shown in the left half of Figure 8, where the arrows show the start and end points of each operation used by the tandem. On the right of Figure 8, the same solution is represented in 2-D physical space, where dashed and continuous arrows represent the drone and truck movements, respectively.

Online supplement B

This online supplement contains the proposed second order cone programming model for the *MVDRP-EL* in a compact form based on the notation introduced in Section 4.

Formulation:

$$\text{minimize } \sum_{o \in O} \text{twait}_t^o \quad (\text{S8})$$

subject to:

$$t_d^o - t_t^o \leq \text{twait}_t^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$\text{earliest}_o \leq s_{o,l} + \sum_{e=0}^{te} x_{e,l}^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S10})$$

$$s_{o,r} + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} x_{e,r}^o \leq \text{latest}_o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S11})$$

$$y_{e,l}^o \leq y_{e-1,l}^o, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te-1\} \quad (\text{S12})$$

$$y_{e,r}^o \leq y_{e-1,r}^o, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te-1\} \quad (\text{S13})$$

$$\sum_{e=0}^{te-1} y_{e,l}^o = s_l^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S14})$$

$$\sum_{e=0}^{te-1} y_{e,r}^o = s_r^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S15})$$

$$y_{e-1,l}^o - y_{e,l}^o \geq x_{e,l}^o, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te-1\} \quad (\text{S16})$$

$$y_{e-1,r}^o - y_{e,r}^o \geq x_{e,r}^o, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te-1\} \quad (\text{S17})$$

$$\text{loc}_r^o = DL + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} \text{ver}_e * (y_{e,r}^o + x_{e,r}^o), \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S18})$$

$$\text{loc}_l^o = DL + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} \text{ver}_e * (y_{e,l}^o + x_{e,l}^o), \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S19})$$

$$s_l^o + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} x_{e,l}^o \leq s_r^o + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} x_{e,r}^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S20})$$

$$s_{o,r} + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} x_{e,r}^o \leq s_{o+1,l} + \sum_{e=0}^{te-1} x_{e,l}^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S21})$$

$$\left(\sum_{e=0}^{te-1} \{ [(y_{e,r}^o + x_{e,r}^o) - (y_{e,l}^o + x_{e,l}^o)] * I(e) \} \right) / \text{Speed}_t \leq t_t^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S22})$$

$$\| \text{loc}_l^o - \text{loc}_{fc}^o \| / \text{Speed}_d \leq \text{tout}_d^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S23})$$

$$\| \text{loc}_r^o - \text{loc}_{fc}^o \| / \text{Speed}_d \leq \text{tin}_d^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S24})$$

$$\text{tout}_d^o + \text{tintra}_d^o + \text{tin}_d^o \leq t_d^o, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S25})$$

$$\text{eout}_d^o = \text{tout}_d^o * e(W(o)), \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S26})$$

$$\text{ein}_d^o = \text{tin}_d^o * e(0), \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S27})$$

$$\text{eh}^o \geq \text{hov} * (t_t^o - t_d^o), \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S28})$$

$$\text{eout}_d^o + \text{eintra}_d^o + \text{ein}_d^o + \text{eh}^o \leq e_{max}, \forall o \in O \quad (\text{S29})$$

$$y_{-1,l}^o = 1, \forall o \in O \quad (S30)$$

$$y_{-1,r}^o = 1, \forall o \in O \quad (S31)$$

$$y_{e,l}^o \in \{0, 1\}, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te - 1\} \quad (S32)$$

$$y_{e,r}^o \in \{0, 1\}, \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te - 1\} \quad (S33)$$

$$s_l^o \in \mathbb{N}, \forall o \in O \quad (S34)$$

$$s_l^{|O|+1} = te \quad (S35)$$

$$s_r^o \in \mathbb{N}, \forall o \in O \quad (S36)$$

$$x_{e,l}^{|O|+1} = 0, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te - 1\} \quad (S37)$$

$$x_{e,l}^o \in [0, 1], \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te - 1\} \quad (S38)$$

$$x_{e,r}^o \in [0, 1], \forall o \in O, \forall e \in \{0, \dots, te - 1\} \quad (S39)$$

$$loc_l^o \in \mathbb{R}^2, \forall o \in O \quad (S40)$$

$$loc_r^o \in \mathbb{R}^2, \forall o \in O \quad (S41)$$

$$t_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S42)$$

$$tout_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S43)$$

$$tin_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S44)$$

$$t_t^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S45)$$

$$twait_t^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S46)$$

$$eout_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S47)$$

$$ein_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S48)$$

$$eh_d^o \geq 0, \forall o \in O \quad (S49)$$

The objective function (S8) minimizes the sum of the truck waiting times. Constraints (S9) set the truck waiting time of each operation to be equal to the difference between the time needed for the drone and the truck to perform the operation. Constraints (S10)/(S11) guarantee that a launch/retrieval location cannot be previous/successive to the earliest launch/latest retrieval one. These constraints are valid cuts in the interest of computational performance, but are not necessary to maintain feasibility. Constraints (S12)/(S13) ensure that an edge cannot be completely traversed before the launch/landing of the drone in an operation if the previous edge has not been completely traversed. Constraints (S14)/(S15) set the number of edges completely traversed equal to the sum of them. Constraints (S16)/(S17) guarantee that an edge can only be partially traversed if the previous edge has been completely traversed. Constraints (S18)/(S19) define the landing/launching position of each operation. Constraints (S20) ensure that the launching position precedes the landing position for each operation. Constraints (S21) guarantee that the landing position of an operation has to precede the launch location of the successive operation. Constraints (S22) define the truck time needed for each operation as the required driving time from the launch location to the rendezvous location. Constraints (S23) and (S24) define for each operation the time needed for the drone to go from the launching position to the first customer location and from the last customer location to the retrieving location, respectively. Constraints (S25) define the time needed for the drone to perform each operation. Constraints (S26) and (S27) define for each operation the energy consumed by the drone to go from the launching position to the first customer location and from the last customer location to the landing position, respectively. Constraints (S28) define the energy needed by

the drone to hover while it is waiting for the truck to arrive. Constraints (S29) limit the drone energy consumption during a single operation to e_{max} . Constraints (S30) to (S49) generally relate to the domain of variables (e.g., constraints related to non-negativity, binary/integer nature of variables, special treatment of variables related to depot location).

Online supplement C

This online supplement contains the detailed results of the lower bound experimentation and the related comparison with the two versions of the solution method ($i\rho_{max} = |V|/2$ and $i\rho_{max} = |V|$) on all the instances with 10 and 20 customers for each value of $|C|$ and $|E_T|$ and on all the instances with 40 customers for each value of $|C|$ and $|E_T| = 90$. The experimentation has been performed considering three different values for the drone speed (2, 4 and 20) and for the endurance (40, 20 and 4). The detailed results considering the drone speed equal to 2 and the endurance equal to 40 of each instance for each combination of $|V|$, $|C|$ and $|E_T|$ tested are reported in Tables C.1-C.7. The detailed results considering the drone speed equal to 4 and the endurance equal to 20 are reported in Tables C.8-C.14. Finally, the detailed results considering the drone speed equal to 20 and the endurance equal to 4 are reported in Tables C.15-C.21. The tables are structured as follow: the first four columns show the instance details; the successive five columns report the details of the lower bound solution (i.e., truck route length, truck waiting time and overheads related to drone sortie setup operation, objective function value, running time); the last four columns reports the percentage gap between the lower bound solution and the proposed method and a Boolean value equal to 1 if the lower bound and the proposed method determine the same truck route, 0 otherwise, resulting from the two versions of the solution method.

TABLE C.1 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 1$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_1_9_1	10	1	9	266.64	0.00	1	267.64	0.15	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_2	10	1	9	151.27	0.00	1	152.27	0.04	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_3	10	1	9	251.77	0.00	1	252.77	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_4	10	1	9	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_5	10	1	9	357.22	0.00	1	358.22	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				261.56	0.00	1.00	262.56	0.06	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
10_1_31_1	10	1	31	182.44	0.00	1	183.44	0.16	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_2	10	1	31	81.77	0.00	1	82.77	0.13	4.33	1	4.33	1
10_1_31_3	10	1	31	244.03	0.00	1	245.03	0.12	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_4	10	1	31	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.26	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_5	10	1	31	219.81	0.00	1	220.81	0.11	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				201.79	0.00	1.00	202.79	0.16	0.87	1.00	0.87	1.00

TABLE C.2 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 4$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_4_9_1	10	4	9	270.55	0.00	1	271.55	0.09	0.37	1	0.37	1
10_4_9_2	10	4	9	299.24	0.00	2	301.24	0.04	9.50	1	9.50	1
10_4_9_3	10	4	9	366.87	0.00	1	367.87	0.05	7.10	1	7.10	1
10_4_9_4	10	4	9	269.91	0.00	1	270.91	0.05	0.74	1	0.74	1
10_4_9_5	10	4	9	438.42	0.00	1	439.42	0.05	0.68	1	0.68	1
Mean				329.00	0.00	1.20	330.20	0.06	3.68	1.00	3.68	1.00
10_4_31_1	10	4	31	229.65	0.00	1	230.65	0.29	0.87	1	0.87	1
10_4_31_2	10	4	31	132.76	2.27	2	137.03	0.28	22.36	1	20.98	1
10_4_31_3	10	4	31	318.21	0.00	1	319.21	0.21	7.94	0	0.63	1
10_4_31_4	10	4	31	216.84	0.00	1	217.84	1.07	0.92	1	0.92	1
10_4_31_5	10	4	31	305.72	0.00	1	306.72	0.27	0.65	1	0.65	1
Mean				240.64	0.45	1.20	242.29	0.42	6.55	0.80	4.81	1.00

TABLE C.3 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 7$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_7_9_1	10	7	9	295.34	0.00	1	296.34	0.08	1.01	1	6.42	1
10_7_9_2	10	7	9	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	0.08	12.69	0	12.69	0
10_7_9_3	10	7	9	279.85	0.00	1	280.85	0.07	26.93	1	26.93	1
10_7_9_4	10	7	9	421.73	0.00	2	423.73	0.05	3.39	1	3.39	1
10_7_9_5	10	7	9	375.01	0.00	1	376.01	0.07	0.80	1	0.53	1
Mean				315.48	0.00	1.20	316.68	0.07	8.97	0.80	9.99	0.80
10_7_31_1	10	7	31	185.09	0.00	1	186.09	3.01	2.15	1	1.61	1
10_7_31_2	10	7	31	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	2.12	18.97	0	10.46	0
10_7_31_3	10	7	31	149.01	0.00	1	150.01	1.16	52.25	0	51.27	0
10_7_31_4	10	7	31	361.46	0.00	2	363.46	1.50	14.97	0	13.86	0
10_7_31_5	10	7	31	190.28	0.00	1	191.28	3.12	27.27	1	27.27	1
Mean				218.26	0.00	1.20	219.46	2.18	23.12	0.40	20.89	0.40

TABLE C.4 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 2$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_2_21_1	20	2	21	184.85	0.00	1	185.85	0.18	0.54	1	9.06	0
20_2_21_2	20	2	21	167.27	0.00	1	168.27	0.15	17.46	0	12.77	1
20_2_21_3	20	2	21	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	0.16	0.65	1	0.65	1
20_2_21_4	20	2	21	57.83	0.00	1	58.83	0.18	6.83	1	6.83	1
20_2_21_5	20	2	21	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	0.17	9.36	0	9.36	0
Mean				143.64	0.00	1.00	144.64	0.17	6.97	0.60	7.74	0.60
20_2_50_1	20	2	50	130.96	0.00	1	131.96	0.80	27.94	0	4.30	1
20_2_50_2	20	2	50	157.64	0.00	1	158.64	2.21	4.56	0	4.56	0
20_2_50_3	20	2	50	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	0.95	0.65	1	0.65	1
20_2_50_4	20	2	50	40.33	0.00	1	41.33	0.98	54.19	0	54.19	0
20_2_50_5	20	2	50	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	0.84	11.34	0	11.34	0
Mean				127.44	0.00	1.00	128.44	1.16	19.74	0.20	15.01	0.40

TABLE C.5 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 8$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_8_21_1	20	8	21	158.70	8.04	2	168.74	1.88	27.37	0	27.37	0
20_8_21_2	20	8	21	331.48	0.00	2	333.48	0.68	0.90	1	0.90	1
20_8_21_3	20	8	21	434.49	0.00	1	435.49	0.81	0.92	1	0.92	1
20_8_21_4	20	8	21	257.54	0.00	1	258.54	0.80	24.18	0	24.18	0
20_8_21_5	20	8	21	436.62	0.00	2	438.62	1.16	2.27	1	2.27	1
Mean				323.76	1.61	1.60	326.97	1.07	11.13	0.60	11.13	0.60
20_8_50_1	20	8	50	130.50	0.00	2	132.50	212.55	44.19	0	43.40	0
20_8_50_2	20	8	50	205.38	5.04	2	212.42	44.72	35.36	0	35.36	0
20_8_50_3	20	8	50	300.38	0.00	2	302.38	11.30	0.66	1	0.66	1
20_8_50_4	20	8	50	121.79	0.00	2	123.79	26.30	67.53	0	53.45	0
20_8_50_5	20	8	50	299.26	0.00	2	301.26	24.90	8.97	0	7.61	0
Mean				211.46	1.01	2.00	214.47	63.95	31.34	0.20	28.10	0.20

TABLE C.6 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 14$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_14_21_1	20	14	21	271.53	0.00	2	273.53	0.83	81.89	0	81.52	0
20_14_21_2	20	14	21	210.11	0.00	1	211.11	1.42	39.77	0	41.59	0
20_14_21_3	20	14	21	346.39	0.00	2	348.39	2.11	23.73	1	18.02	1
20_14_21_4	20	14	21	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	0.72	158.38	1	158.38	1
20_14_21_5	20	14	21	217.87	0.00	2	219.87	2.14	23.80	1	23.54	1
Mean				227.05	0.00	1.60	228.65	1.44	65.51	0.60	64.61	0.60
20_14_50_1	20	14	50	196.77	0.00	3	199.77	26.71	71.28	0	74.62	0
20_14_50_2	20	14	50	201.24	0.00	2	203.24	82.49	13.13	0	13.13	0
20_14_50_3	20	14	50	252.28	0.00	2	254.28	72.81	27.07	0	25.05	0
20_14_50_4	20	14	50	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	5.11	154.83	0	153.23	0
20_14_50_5	20	14	50	189.72	0.00	2	191.72	117.21	39.48	0	40.48	0
Mean				185.87	0.00	2.00	187.87	60.87	61.16	0.00	61.30	0.00

TABLE C.7 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 40$, $|E_T| = 90$, drone speed = 2 and endurance = 40.

Name	V	C	E _T	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
40_4_90_1	40	4	90	228.71	0.00	1	229.71	43.38	6.41	1	6.41	1
40_4_90_2	40	4	90	204.71	0.00	2	206.71	14.51	7.78	0	7.78	0
40_4_90_3	40	4	90	189.76	0.00	2	191.76	20.40	0.52	1	0.52	1
40_4_90_4	40	4	90	168.51	0.00	1	169.51	3.57	18.42	1	18.42	1
40_4_90_5	40	4	90	205.01	0.00	1	206.01	11.72	22.93	0	22.93	0
Mean				199.34	0.00	1.40	200.74	18.71	11.21	0.60	11.21	0.60
40_16_90_1	40	16	90	277.46	0.00	2	279.46	3369.54	15.60	0	15.56	0
40_16_90_2	40	16	90	246.30	0.00	2	248.30	1598.34	17.71	0	11.40	0
40_16_90_3	40	16	90	229.71	0.00	2	231.71	371.22	28.61	0	22.77	0
40_16_90_4	40	16	90	256.79	0.00	2	258.79	537.05	22.20	0	8.78	0
40_16_90_5	40	16	90	344.76	0.00	3	347.76	1417.57	1.00	0	0.63	0
Mean				271.00	0.00	2.20	273.20	1458.74	17.02	0.00	11.83	0.00
40_28_90_1	40	28	90	280.80	0.00	2	282.80	1831.65	30.02	0	35.63	0
40_28_90_2	40	28	90	-	-	-	-	3623.59	-	-	-	-
40_28_90_3	40	28	90	326.01	0.00	2	328.01	3571.64	14.98	0	15.16	0
40_28_90_4	40	28	90	-	-	-	-	3600.00	-	-	-	-
40_28_90_5	40	28	90	354.45	0.00	2	356.45	1821.98	11.30	0	8.74	0
Mean				320.42	0.00	2.00	322.42	2889.77	18.77	0.00	19.84	0.00

TABLE C.8 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 1$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_1_9_1	10	1	9	266.64	0.00	1	267.64	0.04	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_2	10	1	9	151.27	0.00	1	152.27	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_3	10	1	9	251.77	0.00	1	252.77	0.02	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_4	10	1	9	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_5	10	1	9	357.22	0.00	1	358.22	0.03	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				261.56	0.00	1.00	262.56	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
10_1_31_1	10	1	31	182.44	0.00	1	183.44	0.08	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_2	10	1	31	81.77	0.00	1	82.77	0.06	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_3	10	1	31	244.03	0.00	1	245.03	0.10	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_4	10	1	31	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.06	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_5	10	1	31	219.81	0.00	1	220.81	0.06	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				201.79	0.00	1.00	202.79	0.07	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00

TABLE C.9 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 4$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_4_9_1	10	4	9	270.55	0.00	1	271.55	0.03	0.74	1	0.37	1
10_4_9_2	10	4	9	299.24	0.00	2	301.24	0.03	2.53	1	2.53	1
10_4_9_3	10	4	9	366.87	0.00	1	367.87	0.04	2.18	1	1.91	1
10_4_9_4	10	4	9	269.91	0.00	1	270.91	0.03	0.74	1	0.74	1
10_4_9_5	10	4	9	438.42	0.00	1	439.42	0.04	0.68	1	0.68	1
Mean				329.00	0.00	1.20	330.20	0.04	1.37	1.00	1.25	1.00
10_4_31_1	10	4	31	229.65	0.00	1	230.65	0.33	0.87	1	0.87	1
10_4_31_2	10	4	31	132.76	0.00	2	134.76	0.14	6.28	1	5.54	1
10_4_31_3	10	4	31	318.21	0.00	1	319.21	0.14	0.63	1	0.63	1
10_4_31_4	10	4	31	212.44	0.00	2	214.44	0.58	2.52	0	2.52	0
10_4_31_5	10	4	31	305.72	0.00	1	306.72	0.10	0.65	1	0.98	1
Mean				239.76	0.00	1.40	241.16	0.26	2.19	0.80	2.11	0.80

TABLE C.10 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 7$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_7_9_1	10	7	9	295.34	0.00	1	296.34	0.07	1.01	1	0.67	1
10_7_9_2	10	7	9	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	0.05	12.21	0	12.21	0
10_7_9_3	10	7	9	279.85	0.00	1	280.85	0.05	12.72	1	12.72	1
10_7_9_4	10	7	9	421.73	0.00	2	423.73	0.05	0.94	1	0.94	1
10_7_9_5	10	7	9	375.01	0.00	1	376.01	0.04	0.80	1	0.53	1
Mean				315.48	0.00	1.20	316.68	0.05	5.54	0.80	5.42	0.80
10_7_31_1	10	7	31	185.09	0.00	1	186.09	0.25	1.61	1	1.07	1
10_7_31_2	10	7	31	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	0.41	9.97	0	9.97	0
10_7_31_3	10	7	31	149.01	0.00	1	150.01	0.84	27.60	0	27.60	0
10_7_31_4	10	7	31	361.46	0.00	2	363.46	0.39	5.81	1	5.81	1
10_7_31_5	10	7	31	190.28	0.00	1	191.28	0.37	6.70	1	6.70	1
Mean				218.26	0.00	1.20	219.46	0.45	10.34	0.60	10.23	0.60

TABLE C.11 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 2$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_2_21_1	20	2	21	184.85	0.00	1	185.85	0.14	0.54	1	0.54	1
20_2_21_2	20	2	21	167.27	0.00	1	168.27	0.12	17.45	0	0.91	1
20_2_21_3	20	2	21	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	0.08	0.65	1	0.65	1
20_2_21_4	20	2	21	57.83	0.00	1	58.83	0.08	1.70	1	1.70	1
20_2_21_5	20	2	21	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	0.13	10.11	1	10.11	1
Mean				143.64	0.00	1.00	144.64	0.11	6.09	0.80	2.78	1.00
20_2_50_1	20	2	50	130.96	0.00	1	131.96	0.59	0.76	1	0.76	1
20_2_50_2	20	2	50	157.64	0.00	1	158.64	0.28	0.63	1	0.63	1
20_2_50_3	20	2	50	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	0.54	2.64	0	0.65	1
20_2_50_4	20	2	50	40.33	0.00	1	41.33	0.32	2.42	1	2.42	1
20_2_50_5	20	2	50	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	1.86	10.11	1	10.11	1
Mean				127.44	0.00	1.00	128.44	0.72	3.31	0.80	2.91	1.00

TABLE C.12 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 8$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_8_21_1	20	8	21	158.71	0.00	2	160.71	1.04	9.74	1	9.74	1
20_8_21_2	20	8	21	331.48	0.00	2	333.48	0.26	0.90	1	0.90	1
20_8_21_3	20	8	21	460.01	0.00	2	462.01	1.21	2.43	0	0.22	0
20_8_21_4	20	8	21	257.56	0.00	1	258.56	0.56	2.99	1	2.99	1
20_8_21_5	20	8	21	436.62	0.00	2	438.62	1.16	0.68	1	0.68	1
Mean				328.88	0.00	1.80	330.68	0.85	3.35	0.80	2.91	0.80
20_8_50_1	20	8	50	102.01	0.00	2	104.01	9.65	31.24	0	31.24	0
20_8_50_2	20	8	50	205.38	0.00	2	207.38	8.83	35.24	0	35.24	0
20_8_50_3	20	8	50	300.38	0.00	2	302.38	3.23	0.99	1	0.99	1
20_8_50_4	20	8	50	121.79	0.00	2	123.79	1.32	18.65	0	18.65	0
20_8_50_5	20	8	50	299.93	0.00	2	301.93	14.56	1.19	0	0.99	1
Mean				205.90	0.00	2.00	207.90	7.52	17.46	0.20	17.42	0.40

TABLE C.13 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 14$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_14_21_1	20	14	21	271.54	0.00	2	273.54	0.78	65.41	0	65.41	0
20_14_21_2	20	14	21	209.11	0.00	1	210.11	1.37	3.81	1	5.73	1
20_14_21_3	20	14	21	346.39	0.00	2	348.39	2.17	4.56	1	3.99	1
20_14_21_4	20	14	21	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	0.39	51.21	1	51.21	1
20_14_21_5	20	14	21	217.87	0.00	2	219.87	0.60	3.63	1	3.63	1
Mean				226.86	0.00	1.60	228.46	1.06	25.72	0.80	25.99	0.80
20_14_50_1	20	14	50	196.77	0.00	3	199.77	12.92	61.29	0	46.38	0
20_14_50_2	20	14	50	201.24	0.00	2	203.24	6.77	2.95	1	7.32	0
20_14_50_3	20	14	50	252.28	0.00	2	254.28	10.66	8.98	0	6.61	1
20_14_50_4	20	14	50	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	1.49	51.45	1	102.22	0
20_14_50_5	20	14	50	189.72	0.00	2	191.72	19.96	13.80	1	17.53	1
Mean				185.88	0.00	2.00	187.88	10.36	27.69	0.60	36.01	0.40

TABLE C.14 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|E_T| = 90$, drone speed = 4 and endurance = 20.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
40_4_90_1	40	4	90	228.71	0.00	1	229.71	5.79	0.87	1	0.87	1
40_4_90_2	40	4	90	204.72	0.00	2	206.72	13.58	4.64	1	4.64	1
40_4_90_3	40	4	90	189.76	0.00	2	191.76	2.42	0.52	1	0.52	1
40_4_90_4	40	4	90	168.51	0.00	1	169.51	2.06	6.81	1	6.81	1
40_4_90_5	40	4	90	199.92	0.00	1	200.92	2.86	8.26	1	8.26	1
Mean				198.33	0.00	1.40	199.73	5.34	4.22	1.00	4.22	1.00
40_16_90_1	40	16	90	358.80	0.00	4	362.80	85.48	10.56	0	14.02	0
40_16_90_2	40	16	90	203.83	0.00	1	204.83	43.12	18.94	1	18.94	1
40_16_90_3	40	16	90	252.48	0.00	2	254.48	196.65	2.92	0	0.34	0
40_16_90_4	40	16	90	256.48	0.00	2	258.48	78.73	3.21	0	2.83	0
40_16_90_5	40	16	90	312.32	0.00	2	314.32	35.39	2.55	1	5.79	0
Mean				276.78	0.00	2.20	278.98	87.88	7.64	0.40	8.38	0.20
40_28_90_1	40	28	90	250.28	0.00	2	252.28	142.58	21.58	1	15.78	1
40_28_90_2	40	28	90	356.25	0.00	2	358.25	329.27	2.31	0.00	10.61	0.00
40_28_90_3	40	28	90	283.41	0.00	2	285.41	545.14	3.66	0	2.88	0
40_28_90_4	40	28	90	316.88	0.00	2	318.88	157.35	8.32	0.00	8.01	0.00
40_28_90_5	40	28	90	338.19	0.00	2	340.19	125.82	6.75	1	3.53	1
Mean				309.00	0.00	2.00	311.00	260.03	8.52	0.40	8.16	0.40

TABLE C.15 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 1$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_1_9_1	10	1	9	266.64	0.00	1	267.64	0.06	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_2	10	1	9	151.27	0.00	1	152.27	0.06	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_3	10	1	9	251.77	0.00	1	252.77	0.04	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_4	10	1	9	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.05	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_9_5	10	1	9	357.22	0.00	1	358.22	0.05	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				261.56	0.00	1.00	262.56	0.05	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
10_1_31_1	10	1	31	182.44	0.00	1	183.44	0.07	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_2	10	1	31	81.77	0.00	1	82.77	0.07	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_3	10	1	31	244.03	0.00	1	245.03	0.12	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_4	10	1	31	280.89	0.00	1	281.89	0.07	0.00	1	0.00	1
10_1_31_5	10	1	31	219.81	0.00	1	220.81	0.08	0.00	1	0.00	1
Mean				201.79	0.00	1.00	202.79	0.08	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00

TABLE C.16 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 4$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_4_9_1	10	4	9	270.55	0.00	1	271.55	0.04	0.74	1	0.74	1
10_4_9_2	10	4	9	299.24	0.00	2	301.24	0.04	0.33	1	0.33	1
10_4_9_3	10	4	9	366.87	0.00	1	367.87	0.05	0.54	1	0.54	1
10_4_9_4	10	4	9	269.91	0.00	1	270.91	0.04	0.74	1	0.74	1
10_4_9_5	10	4	9	438.42	0.00	1	439.42	0.04	0.46	1	0.46	1
Mean				329.00	0.00	1.20	330.20	0.05	0.56	1.00	0.56	1.00
10_4_31_1	10	4	31	229.65	0.00	1	230.65	0.22	0.87	1	0.87	1
10_4_31_2	10	4	31	132.76	0.00	2	134.76	0.12	0.74	1	0.74	1
10_4_31_3	10	4	31	318.21	0.00	1	319.21	0.18	0.63	1	0.63	1
10_4_31_4	10	4	31	212.44	0.00	2	214.44	0.50	0.00	1	1.85	0
10_4_31_5	10	4	31	305.72	0.00	1	306.72	0.15	0.65	1	0.65	1
Mean				239.76	0.00	1.40	241.16	0.23	0.58	1.00	0.95	0.80

TABLE C.17 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 7$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
10_7_9_1	10	7	9	295.34	0.00	1	296.34	0.07	0.67	1	0.67	1
10_7_9_2	10	7	9	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	0.06	0.97	1	0.97	1
10_7_9_3	10	7	9	279.85	0.00	1	280.85	0.06	2.26	1	2.26	1
10_7_9_4	10	7	9	421.73	0.00	2	423.73	0.06	0.94	1	0.94	1
10_7_9_5	10	7	9	375.01	0.00	1	376.01	0.06	0.53	1	0.53	1
Mean				315.48	0.00	1.20	316.68	0.06	1.08	1.00	1.08	1.00
10_7_31_1	10	7	31	185.09	0.00	1	186.09	0.29	1.07	1	1.07	1
10_7_31_2	10	7	31	205.47	0.00	1	206.47	0.96	0.97	1	0.97	1
10_7_31_3	10	7	31	149.01	0.00	1	150.01	0.29	2.67	1	2.67	1
10_7_31_4	10	7	31	361.46	0.00	2	363.46	0.65	1.43	0	1.43	0
10_7_31_5	10	7	31	190.28	0.00	1	191.28	0.90	1.57	1	1.57	1
Mean				218.26	0.00	1.20	219.46	0.62	1.54	0.80	1.54	0.80

TABLE C.18 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 2$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_2_21_1	20	2	21	184.85	0.00	1	185.85	0.17	0.54	1	0.54	1
20_2_21_2	20	2	21	167.27	0.00	1	168.27	0.14	17.45	0	0.59	1
20_2_21_3	20	2	21	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	0.11	0.65	1	0.65	1
20_2_21_4	20	2	21	57.83	0.00	1	58.83	0.10	1.70	1	1.70	1
20_2_21_5	20	2	21	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	0.12	0.64	1	0.64	1
Mean				143.64	0.00	1.00	144.64	0.13	4.20	0.80	0.82	1.00
20_2_50_1	20	2	50	130.96	0.00	1	131.96	0.40	0.76	1	0.76	1
20_2_50_2	20	2	50	157.64	0.00	1	158.64	0.46	4.56	0	0.63	1
20_2_50_3	20	2	50	152.30	0.00	1	153.30	2.05	0.65	1	0.65	1
20_2_50_4	20	2	50	40.33	0.00	1	41.33	0.28	2.42	1	2.42	1
20_2_50_5	20	2	50	155.96	0.00	1	156.96	0.31	0.64	1	0.64	1
Mean				127.44	0.00	1.00	128.44	0.70	1.81	0.80	1.02	1.00

TABLE C.19 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 20$, $|C| = 8$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_8_21_1	20	8	21	158.71	0.00	2	160.71	0.56	1.87	1	1.87	1
20_8_21_2	20	8	21	331.48	0.00	2	333.48	0.37	0.90	1	0.90	1
20_8_21_3	20	8	21	434.49	0.00	1	435.49	0.48	0.69	1	0.69	1
20_8_21_4	20	8	21	257.56	0.00	1	258.56	0.43	1.55	1	1.55	1
20_8_21_5	20	8	21	436.62	0.00	2	438.62	0.97	0.68	1	0.68	1
Mean				323.77	0.00	1.60	325.37	0.56	1.14	1.00	1.14	1.00
20_8_50_1	20	8	50	130.49	0.00	2	132.49	4.47	2.26	1	2.26	1
20_8_50_2	20	8	50	205.38	0.00	2	207.38	7.20	1.93	1	35.00	0
20_8_50_3	20	8	50	300.38	0.00	2	302.38	4.85	0.66	1	0.66	1
20_8_50_4	20	8	50	121.79	0.00	2	123.79	2.07	3.23	1	3.23	1
20_8_50_5	20	8	50	299.93	0.00	2	301.93	4.35	0.99	1	0.99	1
Mean				211.59	0.00	2.00	213.59	4.59	1.82	1.00	8.43	0.80

TABLE C.20 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 10$, $|C| = 14$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
20_14_21_1	20	14	21	271.54	0.00	2	273.54	0.68	64.90	0	64.90	0
20_14_21_2	20	14	21	209.11	0.00	1	210.11	0.84	2.86	1	3.33	1
20_14_21_3	20	14	21	346.39	0.00	2	348.39	2.31	1.72	1	1.72	1
20_14_21_4	20	14	21	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	0.44	8.56	1	8.56	1
20_14_21_5	20	14	21	217.87	0.00	2	219.87	0.80	2.27	1	2.27	1
Mean				226.86	0.00	1.60	228.46	1.01	16.06	0.80	16.16	0.80
20_14_50_1	20	14	50	196.77	0.00	3	199.77	8.45	57.95	0	40.56	0
20_14_50_2	20	14	50	203.43	0.00	2	205.43	3.17	1.86	0	1.04	0
20_14_50_3	20	14	50	252.28	0.00	2	254.28	14.68	3.83	0	2.36	1
20_14_50_4	20	14	50	89.36	0.00	1	90.36	1.59	8.56	1	8.56	1
20_14_50_5	20	14	50	189.72	0.00	2	191.72	10.22	3.65	1	3.65	1
Mean				186.31	0.00	2.00	188.31	7.62	15.17	0.40	11.23	0.60

TABLE C.21 Comparison of the lower bound and proposed method solutions - Instances with $|V| = 40$, $|E_T| = 90$, drone speed = 20 and endurance = 4.

Name	$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	LB					RTS-EL1		RTS-EL2	
				TR	W	O	CSP	Time	Gap %	ST	Gap %	ST
40_4_90_1	40	4	90	228.71	0.00	1	229.71	3.81	0.87	1	0.87	1
40_4_90_2	40	4	90	204.72	0.00	2	206.72	11.11	0.97	1	0.97	1
40_4_90_3	40	4	90	189.76	0.00	2	191.76	1.74	0.52	1	0.52	1
40_4_90_4	40	4	90	168.51	0.00	1	169.51	1.90	1.18	1	1.18	1
40_4_90_5	40	4	90	205.01	0.00	1	206.01	2.41	0.97	1	0.97	1
Mean				199.34	0.00	1.40	200.74	4.19	0.90	1.00	0.90	1.00
40_16_90_1	40	16	90	276.61	0.00	2	278.61	67.40	6.11	0	6.11	0
40_16_90_2	40	16	90	249.48	0.00	2	251.48	47.05	3.18	1	3.18	1
40_16_90_3	40	16	90	252.48	0.00	3	255.48	85.02	8.92	0	8.11	0
40_16_90_4	40	16	90	295.45	0.00	3	298.45	46.42	9.75	0	9.75	0
40_16_90_5	40	16	90	379.79	0.00	2	381.79	26.92	20.38	0	20.38	0
Mean				290.76	0.00	2.40	293.16	54.56	9.67	0.20	9.51	0.20
40_28_90_1	40	28	90	260.80	0.00	2	262.80	78.36	9.22	0	9.13	0
40_28_90_2	40	28	90	317.54	0.00	3	320.54	81.86	2.50	1.00	2.50	1.00
40_28_90_3	40	28	90	283.41	0.00	2	285.41	77.33	1.59	0	1.59	0
40_28_90_4	40	28	90	319.52	0.00	3	322.52	59.89	0.75	0.00	0.75	0.00
40_28_90_5	40	28	90	338.19	0.00	2	340.19	129.39	2.65	1	2.65	1
Mean				303.89	0.00	2.40	306.29	85.36	3.34	0.40	3.32	0.40

Online supplement D

Our Proposed Solution Method consists of three improvements that are integrated into a single algorithm. We also solved the instances by applying each pairwise combination of the proposed improvements, so obtaining the following procedures:

- $\alpha DRTS1$ - The solution is obtained applying the first phase of the algorithm, with $i\rho_{max} = |V|/2$, to the customer visit orders obtained using different values for α .
- $\alpha DRTS2$ - The solution is obtained applying the first phase of the algorithm, with $i\rho_{max} = |V|$, to the customer visit orders obtained using different values for α .
- $\alpha CRTS$ - The solution is obtained applying the MISOCP to the solutions obtained by the basic RTS for different values of α .
- $DCRTS1$ - The solution is obtained applying the MISOCP to the solution obtained by the procedure $DRTS1$.
- $DCRTS2$ - The solution is obtained applying the MISOCP to the solution obtained by the procedure $DRTS2$.

The resulting objective values and computation times from the of pairwise improvements are shown in Tables D.1 and D.2, respectively (each each row gives an average value calculated over 30 instances). Table D.1 shows the cardinality of V in the first column, and the percentage savings (relative to RTS) obtained applying the solution methods resulting from each pairwise combination in the remaining columns.

From Table D.1, we observe that the best results were obtained using the procedure $DCRTS2$, which reduced objective values by more than 13%, on average. Notably, the two constituent improvements ($DRTS2$ and $CRTS$) were the two individual improvements that produced the most savings in Table 4. Moreover, the savings obtained applying each combination of improvements is greater than the savings achieved using either constituent improvement process.

Table D.2 reports the cardinality of V , and the average computation times of each pairwise improvement combination. First, we observe that the computation times are greater than those of the single improvements. The most time consuming procedures are $\alpha DRTS1$ and $\alpha DRTS2$. This behavior can be explained as the DRTS procedure is relatively time consuming, and it is performed for each distinct value of α . Although $\alpha CRTS$, $DCRTS1$, and $DCRTS2$ required less computational time than the other procedures, they produced the greater savings.

TABLE D.1 Saving (%) for combined improvement approaches

$ V $	$\alpha DRTS1$	$\alpha DRTS2$	$\alpha CRTS$	$DCRTS1$	$DCRTS2$
10	16.20	16.50	18.35	15.99	16.10
20	15.12	16.36	17.64	17.01	18.63
40	11.58	13.73	11.85	15.67	16.60
60	6.34	8.95	7.47	10.70	12.86
80	3.23	4.57	7.26	8.67	8.77
100	3.75	3.95	6.97	7.77	8.18
Mean	9.37	10.68	11.59	12.63	13.53

TABLE D.2 Times for combined approaches

$ V $	$\alpha DRTS1$	$\alpha DRTS2$	$\alpha CRTS$	$DCRTS1$	$DCRTS2$
10	1.31	1.98	1.12	0.86	1.23
20	8.57	16.82	2.52	2.25	3.82
40	37.70	84.76	7.13	6.39	13.02
60	95.06	269.88	17.74	15.13	39.71
80	234.82	657.63	36.80	27.21	77.69
100	396.10	1221.32	67.30	46.53	135.01
Mean	128.93	375.40	22.10	16.40	45.08

Online supplement E

This online supplement contains the aggregated results for each combination of $|V|$, $|C|$, and $|E_T|$ averaged over the 5 generated instances. Tables E.1 and E.2 contain the savings and the times solving the instances with each single improvement, respectively. Moreover, Tables E.3 and E.4 show the savings and the times when the instances are solved using each pairwise combination of the improvements. Finally, Table E.5 shows the results from solving the instances through the two versions of the solution method ($ip_{max} = |V|/2$ and $ip_{max} = |V|$).

TABLE E.1 Savings (%) of single improvement approaches

V	C	E _T	α RTS	DRTS1	DRTS2	CRTS
10	1	9	0.000	11.275	11.275	7.297
10	1	31	0.000	1.754	1.754	7.098
10	4	9	12.445	20.378	21.543	13.412
10	7	9	11.750	14.044	19.542	14.044
10	7	9	9.679	8.028	7.114	14.503
10	7	31	10.238	4.244	5.914	13.467
20	2	21	0.000	10.711	9.118	13.842
20	2	50	0.000	9.741	12.015	11.276
20	8	21	5.760	11.212	12.228	14.921
20	8	50	3.664	8.514	11.351	15.553
20	14	21	6.033	18.527	18.481	17.419
20	14	50	2.743	14.779	17.628	12.517
40	4	90	0.469	7.567	8.086	1.564
40	4	211	0.004	4.515	6.371	2.292
40	16	90	1.728	18.056	22.162	15.519
40	16	211	2.253	9.831	10.702	12.212
40	28	90	0.805	18.049	17.957	21.834
40	28	211	2.398	4.057	8.872	8.313
60	6	205	0.542	12.921	15.816	2.560
60	6	467	0.000	2.285	2.185	0.665
60	24	205	0.324	7.860	11.074	7.606
60	24	467	0.124	0.273	4.895	4.096
60	42	205	3.978	8.859	9.894	12.993
60	42	467	2.179	0.404	2.930	7.119
80	8	311	0.000	22.517	19.046	6.975
80	8	798	0.095	1.167	2.121	3.400
80	32	311	0.476	6.382	6.952	11.137
80	32	798	0.542	0.261	1.800	4.461
80	56	311	0.876	1.337	8.183	8.859
80	56	798	0.714	0.144	1.515	4.686
100	10	483	1.655	6.698	6.155	5.160
100	10	1245	0.219	1.095	2.170	2.689
100	40	483	2.114	5.901	5.476	7.000
100	40	1245	1.866	0.000	0.000	4.301
100	70	483	0.327	3.031	5.103	8.717
100	70	1245	0.183	0.000	0.000	5.404
Mean			2.394	7.959	9.042	8.993

TABLE E.2 Times of single improvement approaches

$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	RTS	α RTS	DRTS1	DRTS2	CRTS
10	1	9	0.005	0.005	0.337	0.781	0.229
10	1	31	0.010	0.010	0.345	0.640	0.238
10	4	9	0.008	0.017	0.441	0.559	0.333
10	4	31	0.012	0.033	0.603	0.787	0.322
10	7	9	0.011	0.058	0.497	0.852	0.538
10	7	31	0.216	0.429	0.531	1.144	0.729
20	2	21	0.026	0.196	0.956	2.359	0.139
20	2	50	0.038	0.197	1.201	2.803	0.146
20	8	21	0.063	0.501	1.951	2.879	0.357
20	8	50	0.124	0.928	2.122	3.831	0.353
20	14	21	0.055	0.820	2.260	3.608	0.581
20	14	50	0.127	1.126	2.616	4.914	0.554
40	4	90	0.114	0.616	3.987	8.298	0.327
40	4	211	0.210	0.661	3.453	9.039	0.447
40	16	90	0.230	2.253	7.092	15.415	0.946
40	16	211	0.280	2.010	6.668	14.110	0.708
40	28	90	0.404	4.432	11.162	22.719	1.483
40	28	211	0.441	3.976	7.353	21.185	1.391
60	6	205	0.376	1.173	10.652	25.242	0.677
60	6	467	0.562	1.937	8.852	17.247	0.889
60	24	205	0.708	5.823	15.839	43.401	1.513
60	24	467	0.840	6.261	8.526	32.668	1.679
60	42	205	1.098	12.634	24.850	65.219	2.879
60	42	467	1.341	14.741	17.530	45.595	2.970
80	8	311	0.643	2.925	18.227	42.890	1.209
80	8	798	0.918	2.771	10.112	31.088	1.457
80	32	311	1.680	17.810	37.648	101.450	3.615
80	32	798	2.008	18.738	18.762	47.706	3.764
80	56	311	2.576	30.494	43.808	148.874	5.040
80	56	798	3.120	33.096	28.276	86.810	6.067
100	10	483	1.257	7.287	38.513	94.128	2.189
100	10	1245	1.594	7.318	27.774	64.931	2.648
100	40	483	3.060	31.599	52.536	194.523	4.186
100	40	1245	3.770	32.948	28.710	64.356	4.722
100	70	483	5.026	59.011	79.461	287.512	8.895
100	70	1245	6.113	68.162	44.299	95.618	10.813
Mean			1.085	10.361	15.776	44.588	2.084

TABLE E.3 Saving (%) for combined improvement approaches

$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	$\alpha DRTS1$	$\alpha DRTS2$	$\alpha CRTS$	$DCRTS1$	$DCRTS2$
10	1	9	11.275	11.275	7.297	12.191	12.191
10	1	31	1.754	1.754	7.098	7.098	7.098
10	4	9	22.199	22.712	23.939	23.226	23.226
10	4	31	27.264	28.636	27.805	25.413	25.522
10	7	9	17.942	17.186	23.239	14.556	14.147
10	7	31	16.791	17.416	20.743	13.429	14.427
20	2	21	10.711	9.118	13.842	13.842	13.157
20	2	50	9.741	12.015	11.276	11.276	14.429
20	8	21	15.789	16.972	21.224	16.873	16.873
20	8	50	14.393	17.154	20.481	11.495	18.208
20	14	21	23.050	23.484	23.989	27.417	27.970
20	14	50	17.046	19.411	15.032	21.183	21.142
40	4	90	7.567	8.086	2.049	8.853	8.853
40	4	211	4.556	6.570	6.360	6.326	9.848
40	16	90	18.290	22.399	15.950	24.169	27.513
40	16	211	11.536	11.874	12.950	14.644	14.129
40	28	90	19.755	21.644	22.736	29.676	25.982
40	28	211	7.768	11.786	11.050	10.326	13.282
60	6	205	12.921	15.816	4.009	15.852	19.331
60	6	467	2.285	3.366	0.665	3.939	5.261
60	24	205	9.601	14.315	9.734	14.583	16.847
60	24	467	2.070	6.893	6.706	5.282	9.054
60	42	205	8.998	10.229	15.753	18.428	18.642
60	42	467	2.179	3.107	7.939	6.093	8.015
80	8	311	5.580	5.320	7.713	9.572	6.737
80	8	798	1.291	2.246	3.400	4.127	4.892
80	32	311	6.693	7.246	11.815	16.268	14.418
80	32	798	0.803	2.342	5.028	5.630	5.960
80	56	311	4.146	8.771	9.872	10.651	13.402
80	56	798	0.858	1.515	5.745	5.774	7.238
100	10	483	8.947	6.779	7.122	8.613	9.638
100	10	1245	1.095	2.501	2.689	3.854	4.476
100	40	483	7.382	7.293	10.192	12.479	12.976
100	40	1245	1.866	1.866	5.688	4.301	4.301
100	70	483	3.031	5.103	8.817	11.993	12.314
100	70	1245	0.183	0.183	7.295	5.404	5.404
Mean			9.371	10.677	11.590	12.634	13.525

TABLE E.4 Times for combined approaches

$ V $	$ C $	$ E_T $	$\alpha DRTS1$	$\alpha DRTS2$	$\alpha CRTS$	$DCRTS1$	$DCRTS2$
10	1	9	0.337	0.781	0.229	0.607	1.109
10	1	31	0.345	0.640	0.238	0.633	0.978
10	4	9	1.410	1.585	1.074	0.800	0.989
10	4	31	1.960	2.492	1.141	0.992	1.208
10	7	9	1.930	3.166	1.978	1.058	1.410
10	7	31	1.861	3.192	2.069	1.054	1.713
20	2	21	1.126	2.530	0.309	1.115	2.582
20	2	50	1.359	2.962	0.305	1.381	3.031
20	8	21	8.716	13.190	1.911	2.487	3.358
20	8	50	10.799	23.208	2.932	2.432	4.209
20	14	21	16.253	29.653	5.090	2.832	4.380
20	14	50	13.194	29.364	4.594	3.234	5.369
40	4	90	13.996	29.086	1.375	4.255	8.720
40	4	211	8.497	21.832	1.210	3.741	9.437
40	16	90	58.454	126.956	9.255	7.829	16.210
40	16	211	35.128	79.170	5.545	7.169	14.723
40	28	90	96.943	222.140	20.814	12.128	23.681
40	28	211	47.985	130.886	12.182	8.086	21.929
60	6	205	26.706	62.634	2.099	11.094	25.764
60	6	467	23.251	65.729	3.035	9.286	21.165
60	24	205	130.761	316.645	14.519	16.539	44.195
60	24	467	69.684	241.629	12.276	9.227	33.418
60	42	205	211.636	648.063	40.785	26.002	66.507
60	42	467	108.318	284.590	33.751	18.625	47.196
80	8	311	68.663	181.041	5.014	18.758	43.552
80	8	798	34.227	96.991	4.226	10.697	31.864
80	32	311	380.008	979.385	41.270	38.620	102.648
80	32	798	170.631	513.599	32.746	19.838	48.925
80	56	311	515.811	1555.306	75.659	45.298	150.434
80	56	798	239.562	619.437	61.888	30.066	88.717
100	10	483	187.952	499.387	11.686	39.190	95.028
100	10	1245	83.165	275.734	10.793	28.581	66.029
100	40	483	539.700	1877.957	58.606	53.781	195.901
100	40	1245	242.911	623.361	45.485	29.842	65.701
100	70	483	875.954	3049.412	129.568	81.393	289.471
100	70	1245	446.891	1002.058	147.653	46.413	97.933
Mean			129.892	378.216	22.314	16.530	45.541

TABLE E.5 Solution method results

V	C	E _T	Savings		Time	
			RTS-EL1	RTS-EL2	RTS-EL1	RTS-EL2
10	1	9	12.191	12.191	0.607	1.109
10	1	31	7.098	7.098	0.633	0.978
10	4	9	24.231	24.231	2.249	2.559
10	4	31	31.430	32.698	2.972	3.655
10	7	9	24.291	23.421	3.611	4.971
10	7	31	24.291	23.421	3.611	4.971
20	2	21	13.842	13.157	1.285	2.753
20	2	50	11.276	14.429	1.540	3.189
20	8	21	22.275	22.275	10.357	15.007
20	8	50	17.988	23.502	12.711	25.412
20	14	21	31.441	32.036	17.987	32.921
20	14	50	23.501	23.393	21.044	36.024
40	4	90	9.339	9.339	14.974	30.450
40	4	211	8.951	10.784	9.207	22.772
40	16	90	24.951	28.177	66.204	135.615
40	16	211	14.838	16.886	32.071	72.800
40	28	90	30.453	29.374	110.302	242.636
40	28	211	16.242	19.008	56.161	139.285
60	6	205	15.852	19.331	28.129	64.118
60	6	467	3.939	5.261	24.718	67.615
60	24	205	16.425	18.399	139.550	326.720
60	24	467	7.852	11.191	75.282	247.553
60	42	205	19.219	19.092	243.821	676.766
60	42	467	8.366	9.395	125.338	304.658
80	8	311	10.140	8.340	71.033	184.030
80	8	798	4.127	4.892	35.870	99.123
80	32	311	16.268	15.314	399.121	1001.748
80	32	798	6.196	6.789	181.964	527.012
80	56	311	12.478	14.837	548.807	1595.676
80	56	798	6.617	7.425	263.995	645.636
100	10	483	12.414	11.068	192.494	505.227
100	10	1245	3.854	5.300	86.643	280.434
100	40	483	13.844	14.995	561.683	1908.834
100	40	1245	5.688	5.688	255.230	637.596
100	70	483	12.052	12.314	936.565	3103.468
100	70	1245	7.295	7.295	512.813	1068.108
Mean			14.638	15.570	140.284	389.475